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Helioptrium indicum L. (Hatisur), a traditional remedy for antifertility from baigas of Sonaghati, Uttar Pradesh, India

Juhi Singh

Abstract

Helioptrium indicum L. commonly known as Hatisur belongs to Boraginaceae family has rich history of ethnobotanical uses. Survey of literature mentions that it has large number of bioactive compounds and is used in rheumatism, wound healing, bone fracture, antifertility, snake bite etc. The district Sonbhadra is rich in biodiversity and large number of tribes live in various parts of it. Baigas are one of the prominent tribe which is still dependent on the surrounding flora for its livelihood and medicinal needs. Hatisur is one of important plant which is used by Baigas for treatment for antifertility. The present paper reveals the use of *Helioptrium indicum* in the case of antifertility.

Keywords: *Helioptrium indicum*, Baigas, antifertility

Introduction

Helioptrium indicum L. is member of family Boraginaceae is a perennial herb, strigose to woolly, up to 30 cm high. Leaves alternate or subopposite, broadly ovate or ovate-oblong. Flowers in extra axillary up to 15 cm long, ebracteate spikes, scorpioid at the apex. Calyx-lobes linear. Corolla blue mauve; lobes small, rounded, crenate. Drupes deeply 2 lobed, conical or ovoid; nutlets compressed, 4 ribbed, beaked 2 seeded. Research shows that the plant extract has potential antifertility and abortifacient affect which validates the ethnomedicinal use of this plant as an antifertility agent (Andhiwal *et al* 2013) [1]. The n-hexane and benzene fractions of the ethanol extract of the whole plant also showed antifertility activity using antiimplantation and abortifacient models in rats (Savadi, 2009) [3]. The findings suggest that the plant contains many important phytochemicals, including pyrrolizidine alkaloids, indicine, echinidine, supinine, heleurine, heliotrine, lasiocarpine, acetyl indicine, indicinine, indicine N-oxide, cynoglossine, europine N-oxide, heleurine N-oxide, heliotridine N-oxide, heliotrine N-oxide, heliotrine, volatile oils, triterpenes, amines, and sterols. Scientific reports revealed that the herb showed antioxidant, analgesic, antimicrobial, anticancer, antituberculosis, antiplasmodial, anticataract, antifertility, wound healing, antiinflammatory, antinociceptive, antihyperglycemic, anthelmintic, diuretic, antitussive, antiglaucoma, antiallergic, and larvicidal activity (Sarkar *et al.* 2021) [2].

The area of ethnobotanical survey is Sonbhadra district which is second largest district by area of Uttar Pradesh. It is the valley of river Son and Belan. The district lies in Vindhyan Plateau between 23° 45' to 24° 34'N latitude and 82° 45' to 83° 23'E longitude and elevation above the mean sea level ranges between 315 m to 485 m (Singh and Singh, 1991) [4]. The district Sonbhadra is rich in forest which covers about 70% of its total geographical area, which is tropical dry deciduous type. This area is inhabited by several tribes such as Gond, Mushar, Bhil, Agariya, Baiga, Bhuiya, Chero, Kharwar, Panika, Pahariya and Patari (Singh, A.K. *et al.* 2002) [5]. The Baiga tribe of Sonbhadra district have great knowledge of medicinal value and have potent remedy of *Helioptrium indicum* L. as an antifertility agent and abortifacient agent when applied to females.

As an abortifacient agent paste of the entire plant is injected inside the uterus after conception for 7 days regularly. The pregnancy gets aborted within 2-3 days. As an antifertility agent the paste of entire plant has to be injected intravaginally.

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Conclusion

It has been reported that the plant has tremendous potential bioactive secondary metabolites such as pyrrolizidine, alkaloids, flavonoids, quinones and terpenoids and thus the species is appreciated for its antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic activities and thus it may improve therapeutic importance in coming future.

References

1. Andhiwal CK, Has C, Varshney RP. Chemical and pharmacological studies of *Heliotropium indicum*. Indian Drugs. 2013;22(11):567-569.
2. Sarkar C, Mondal M, Khanom B, Hossain MM, Hossain MS, Antony S, et al. *Heliotropium indicum* L.: From farm to a source of bioactive compounds with therapeutic activity. Evid Based Complement Alternat Med. 2021.
3. Savadi RV, Alagawadi KR, Darade SS. Antifertility activity of ethanolic extract and its n-hexane and benzene fractions of *Heliotropium indicum* leaves on albino rats. J Pharm Res. 2009;2(5):927-930.
4. Singh JS, Singh KP, Agarwal M. Environmental degradation of Obra-Renukoot Singrauli area, India and its impact on natural and derived ecosystem. Environ. 1991;11:171-180.
5. Singh AK, Raghuvanshi AS, Singh JS. Medical ethnobotany of tribals of Sonaghati of Sonbhadra District, Uttar Pradesh, India. J Ethnopharmacol. 2002;81(1):31-41.

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